

NOTARY IN CIVIL PROCEEDINGS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The notary, as one of the important institutions that ensures the rights of individuals and legal entities, performing the functions of preventive justice and the prevention of legal disputes, became one of the first legal institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan that underwent optimization. In particular, we are talking about the difference between cross-border and national legal requirements regarding the execution of documents, the need or absence of the need to certify individual documents, the procedure for their execution and other differences

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The gradual transformation of state notaries into private practitioners, as is happening in all countries with Latin-type notaries, is intended to increase the role of the institution in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, as well as to bring the quality of services provided by notaries to a modern high level.

Each individual case of notarial actions in practice is a unique phenomenon, however, even the most studied and simple issues can sometimes cause complications in the notarial process, and in the case of an insufficiently responsible approach, quite negative consequences.

To protect the property rights of citizens and legal entities, the law establishes that a notary engaged in private practice is liable with his property for obligations arising from causing property damage to an individual or legal entity and (or) third parties when performing notarial acts.

A number of new notarial actions have been introduced, such as: providing evidence in pre-trial proceedings, acting as an intermediary in property and inheritance issues, confirming the time of filing copyright and related rights. In addition, it is now possible to execute most notarial acts on the principle of extraterritoriality. Accordingly, individuals and legal entities have the opportunity to execute notarial acts in any region, regardless of their place of residence.

In accordance with Article 31 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Notaries”, Notarial actions are performed after payment on the day of submission of all necessary documents.

The performance of a notarial act may be postponed if it is necessary to request additional information or send documents for examination.

The performance of notarial actions should be postponed if, by force of law, it is necessary to ask interested parties that they have no objections to performing these actions. The period for which the performance of a notarial act is postponed cannot exceed one month. At the request of the person who applied for the performance of a notarial act, he is issued a resolution to postpone the performance of a notarial act.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in accordance with the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, transactions made by a notary certainly require a certified power of attorney.¹

An important factor that notaries must take into account is the procedure for the execution of acts, which is usually based on the principles of voluntary execution, however, some international treaties regulate the forced execution of notarial acts with an executive signature, in addition to judicial ones. Formed in one state, acts must be enforced in another state. Due to the fact that the subject of notarial action is an official act, its execution must be carried out on the basis of legal order, as well as it is necessary to clarify the specifics of the application of such acts on the territory of another state.

Before starting to work with official documentation, the notary must comprehensively analyze the specific situation and search for connections between the elements of the legal relationship. The notary must receive an answer to several fundamental questions: what is the object and subject of legal relations, what rights and obligations do the parties have in relation to each other, to counterparties, to the state, to other states. Due to the fact that the notary, as is customary, relies on the information provided to him by the parties, evaluating and analyzing it, already at the initial stage it is necessary to obtain information about the location of persons and property, their origin, as well as the result that the parties are trying to achieve when applying to the notary.

According to Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of November 18, 2020 No. 726, notarial acts are performed by notaries on the premises of a notary office or at the request of applicants on an offsite basis. When performing

¹Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Part two. Electronic resource: <https://lex.uz/docs/180550a>

notarial acts outside the premises of a notary's office, the certification inscription on the document indicates the address of the place where the transaction was completed, and the process of drawing up and signing the power of attorney is necessarily recorded on audio and video.

When audio and video recording of the transaction process, the notary and the persons participating in the notarial act must be fully captured in the photo. At the same time, the process of signing and scanning fingerprints in the automated information system “notary” (hereinafter referred to as the system) with confirmation that the notary aloud explains to the parties what notarial action is being performed, the content, meaning of the notarial action, and that the parties are fully familiar with the text of the document and corresponds to its original purpose, carried out in full audio and form. the video must be recorded.

In accordance with Article 11 of the Law “On Notaries,” notarial acts in the Republic of Uzbekistan are performed in the state language. The text of the document being drawn up is issued by a notary at the request of citizens in Russian or, if possible, in another acceptable language.

If the power of attorney is drawn up in a language that the applicant does not understand or does not know well, then the text of the document can be orally translated by a notary or translator invited by the applicant. The text of the document and the certification inscription must indicate who translated it, the name of the identity document, its number, the date of issue and the name of the authority that issued this document, as well as the content of the text. In this case, the applicant writes and signs his full name, surname, and patronymic in the language he knows.

Moreover, the notary must clearly understand the types and scope of legal consequences that may arise after the completion of notarial actions. The notary must take into account the fact that the category of legal situations that clients address is quite wide, and some of them are provided in the legal literature.²

The Law “On Notaries” also establishes the procedure for a notary to apply the norms of foreign law and contains instructions regarding the performance of certain notarial actions. If it is necessary for a notary to refer to the norms of an international treaty, Art. 93 of this Law indicates the priority of application of an

²Medvedev I.G. International private law and notarial activity // M., Wolters Kluwer, 2005 – p. 6

international treaty, which is also specified in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Republic of Uzbekistan is a party to many bilateral agreements on legal assistance. These treaties contain some principles and procedures for cooperation between states, competent government structures and organizations, the procedure for recognizing the legal force of documents and other provisions regarding international relations in the field of law in general and notarial activities.

In the practice of notaries, there are situations when it is impossible to apply the norms of foreign law.

For example, a notary fails to establish the necessary conflict of laws rule after all the attempts made, and he is forced to use the rules of national substantive law, or the foreign order contradicts the mandatory rules of national legislation.

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